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Revised Accuracy Analysis for the Star Mapper

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The average count rate as a star of magnitude B traverses one of the slit systems is

$$I_0 = \delta k_e A 10^{-0.4(B-9)} \int F_\lambda(B-V) \cdot T_\lambda \cdot Q_\lambda d\lambda \quad [Hz] \quad (1)$$

where δ is the ratio r/s (r = slit width along y , s = grid period along y), $k_e = 0.9$ is the counting efficiency, $A = 176.6 \text{ cm}^2$ the entrance pupil area (obstr. ratio 0.56), and $F_\lambda(B-V)$, T_λ , Q_λ respectively the monochromatic flux for a $B=9$ star of colour $B-V$, the instrument transmittance, and the detector quantum efficiency. With $F_\lambda, T_\lambda, Q_\lambda$ from Table 1 we obtain approximately

$$I_0(B, B-V, S20) \approx 4.0 \cdot 10^7 \cdot 10^{-0.4[B - 0.59(B-V)]} \cdot \delta \quad [Hz] \quad (2a)$$

$$I_0(B, B-V, biakali) \approx 3.8 \cdot 10^7 \cdot 10^{-0.4[B - 0.31(B-V)]} \cdot \delta \quad [Hz] \quad (2b)$$

for S20 and biakali sensitivity type, respectively.

The effective modulation of the stellar count rate is of the form

$$I_s(t) = I_0 \left\{ 1 + \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \cos[k 2\pi v(t-t_0)/s - k\phi_k] \right\} \quad (3)$$

where $v = 150 \text{ arcs/s}$, t_0 = transit time, ϕ_k = small phase shifts due to unsymmetrical aberrations. The modulation coefficients are the flux-weighted means of the monochromatic coefficients

$$a_k(\lambda) = 2 M(k\lambda/s, \theta k\lambda/s) \frac{\sin(k\pi\delta)}{k\pi\delta} \frac{\sin(k\pi v\Delta t/s)}{k\pi v\Delta t/s} \quad (4)$$

$$a_k = \int a_k(\lambda) F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda d\lambda / \int F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda d\lambda \quad (5)$$

Δt = sampling period, $M(y, z)$ = two-dimensional (normalized) MTF, θ = slope of slit system ($\theta = \tan i$, i = inclination of slits to z axis).

For an aberration-free instrument, $M(y, z)$ is the autocorrelation of the pupil (Fig. 1); for the present calculations we have (rather arbitrarily) degraded the ideal MTF by a factor $1 - 0.8\zeta(1-\zeta)$, where $\zeta \equiv y/D$ is the normalized spatial frequency along y ($D = 0.25 \text{ m}$ is the pupil length along y).

(2)

The resulting MTF at $\theta = 0, 0.5,$ and 1 is shown in Fig. 2. Examples of the corresponding intensity modulation curves are given in Fig. 3.

The timing accuracy for the intensity modulation $I_s(t), 0 \leq t \leq T,$ is given by the Cramér-Rao bound

$$\sigma_{t_0}^{-2} = \int_0^T [I_s'(t)]^2 / I_s(t) \cdot dt, \quad (6)$$

which in our case becomes (after conversion to angular accuracy, and neglecting ϕ_k)

$$\sigma^2 \approx \frac{1}{N_s} \left(\frac{s}{2\pi} \right)^2 \left\langle \frac{(\sum_k k a_k \sin k\psi)^2}{1 + \sum_k a_k \cos k\psi} \right\rangle^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where $N_s = T I_0 = \int_0^T I_s(t) dt$ is the total number of photons detected, and $\langle \rangle$ denotes average with respect to the modulation phase angle $\psi \equiv 2\pi\nu(t-t_0)/s$.

In case we add a constant background count rate I_b , we must replace N_s in (7) by the total number of counts $N_s + N_b$, where $N_b = T I_b$, and modify the modulation coefficients according to

$$a_k := \frac{a_k}{1 + N_b/N_s} \quad (8)$$

As a practical rule we have found the following approximation:

$$\sigma^2 \approx \frac{E(s, r, \theta, pk)}{N_s} 10^{c_1(\beta-\nu)} (1 + c_2 N_b/N_s) [1 + c_3 (\Delta t \cdot \nu/s)^2] \quad (9)$$

where $E, c_1, c_2,$ and c_3 are "constants" depending on $s, r, \theta,$ and $pk =$ photocathode type, according to the table below:

slit period (s)	slit width (r)	slit inclination (θ)	photocathode (pk)	E [arcsec ²]	c_1 [-]	c_2 [-]	c_3 [-]
3"	0.3"	0.0	S20	0.0824	0.050	0.50	45
			bialkali	0.0761	0.019	0.50	45
3"	0.7"	0.5	S20	0.485	0.079	0.86	8.0
			bialkali	0.444	0.044	0.86	8.0
3"	1.0"	1.0	S20	1.65	0.136	1.00	4.0
			bialkali	1.41	0.073	1.00	4.0

The background count rate is

$$I_b = I_d(\text{pkc}) + I_{\text{sky}} \quad (10)$$

where I_d is the dark count rate, taken as $I_d(520) = 1500 \text{ Hz}$ and $I_d(\text{biatkeci}) = 100 \text{ Hz}$ ($\sim 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ phototube, $+20^\circ\text{C}$). The sky background depends on the total slit area (α , in arcsec² per FOV) and the sky brightness, which can be specified as the blue magnitude for a 1 arcsec² area, B_{sky} ($B-V_{\text{sky}} \approx 0.7$). By means of (2) we find

$$I_{\text{sky}}(B_{\text{sky}}, 520) \approx 1.2 \cdot 10^8 \alpha 10^{-0.4 B_{\text{sky}}} \quad [\text{Hz}] \quad (11a)$$

$$I_{\text{sky}}(B_{\text{sky}}, \text{biatkeci}) \approx 0.9 \cdot 10^8 \alpha 10^{-0.4 B_{\text{sky}}} \quad [\text{Hz}] \quad (11b)$$

According to Allen (Astrophysical Quantities, 1973), mean sky brightness corresponds to $B_{\text{sky}} \approx 22.5$ which we shall call "dark sky". Due to scattered light from the Earth, sky brightness may temporarily be considerably higher; we consider also $B_{\text{sky}} = 20.0$ ($10 \times$ dark sky) and $B_{\text{sky}} = 17.5$ ($100 \times$ dark sky).

The photometric accuracy of derived stellar counts, $N_s = (N_s + N_b) - N_b$,

is $\sigma_{N_s}^2 = N_s + 2N_b$, or in magnitudes

$$\sigma_m \approx \frac{1.086}{\sqrt{N_s}} \left(1 + 2 \frac{N_b}{N_s}\right)^{1/2} \quad \left(\text{no factor 2 if } N_b \text{ is determined for a much longer time interval}\right) \quad (12)$$

According to (2) we may obtain the colour as

$$B-V \approx \text{const.} + \frac{2.5 \lg [N_s(520)] - 2.5 \lg [N_s(\text{biatkeci})]}{0.59 - 0.31} \quad (13)$$

from which the expected accuracy is

$$\sigma_{B-V} \approx 3.57 \sqrt{\sigma_m^2(520) + \sigma_m^2(\text{biatkeci})} \quad (14)$$

(Table 2).

Fig. 1. Entrance pupil as viewed from one of the star mapper grids. The central obstruction is slightly eccentric because it is physically located ≈ 0.75 m behind the pupil (field angle at star mapper $\eta \approx 0.75^\circ$). Below are three slit systems with identical periods along y (or η), but different inclinations: 0° , 26.565° , and 45° , corresponding to slope = 0, 0.5, 1.0.

Fig. 2. Normalized MTF for the pupil and slit orientations shown in Fig. 1. The abscissa is the spatial frequency normalized to the full length of the pupil, 0.25 m. Also shown are the frequencies of the various harmonics of a slit system with period $s = 3''$ (for wavelength 500 nm).

Fig. 3. Normalized intensity modulation curves for slit systems with period $s = 3''$ and different orientations: slope = 0.0 (slit width $r = 0.3''$), slope = 0.5 ($r = 0.7''$), and slope = 1.0 ($r = 1.0''$). Sampling rate 600 Hz, $B-V = 0.6$, S20 sensitivity.

Fig. 4a. Mean error for the transit of a $B = 9$ star ($B - V = 0.6$) across a system of 8 vertical (slope = 0) slits ($s = 3''$), versus slit width r . The curve "no background" assumes dark count rate + sky = 0 Hz. The other curves assume dark count rate = 1500 Hz (S20 photocathode) and a sky brightness corresponding to $B = 22.5$ mag/arcsec² ("dark sky") or $B = 20.0$ mag/arcsec² (10 x), with a total slit area of $9600 + 19200r$ arcsec² per FOV.

Fig. 4b. Same as Fig. 4a but for slope = 0.5 and total slit area of $19200r$ arcsec² per FOV.

Fig. 4c. Same as Fig. 4a but for slope = 1.0 and total slit area $5760 + 9600r$ arcsec².

Fig. 5. Degradation of accuracy with increasing sample period (Δt).

CONFIGURATION A: 8 vertical slits (slope = 0, width $r = 0.3''$, height = 20')
8 inclined slits (slope = 1, width $r = 1.0''$, height = 20')

CONFIGURATION B: 8 inclined slits (slope = $+\frac{1}{2}$, width $r = 0.7''$, height = 20')
8 inclined slits (slope = $-\frac{1}{2}$, width $r = 0.7''$, height = 20')

CONFIGURATION C: 8 vertical slits (slope = 0, width $r = 0.3''$, height = 40')
8 inclined slits (slope = 1, width $r = 1.0''$, height = 20')

Fig. 6. The three slit configurations compared in Table 3. The grid period is always $s = 3''$ along y . Note that the slit width, r , refers to the width along y ; the actual width (perpendicular to the slit) is $r(1 + \text{slope}^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$.

Table 1. Adopted stellar fluxes (F_λ , in photons $s^{-1} m^{-2} nm^{-1}$ for $B = 9$), instrument transmittance (T_λ , from MATRA report), and detector quantum efficiencies (Q_λ).

λ (nm)	$10^{-4} F_\lambda$				T_λ	Q_λ	
	$B-V = -0.25$	0.25	0.75	1.25		S20	bialkali
375	4.27	2.45	1.66	1.10	0.11	0.17	0.20
400	4.17	3.80	2.51	1.86	0.50	0.17	0.20
425	3.80	4.07	2.88	2.57	0.66	0.16	0.19
450	3.39	4.07	4.47	5.37	0.72	0.15	0.18
475	2.95	3.89	4.90	5.50	0.78	0.12	0.14
500	2.40	3.39	4.57	5.89	0.82	0.11	0.12
525	2.24	3.39	4.68	6.61	0.85	0.09	0.09
550	2.00	3.31	5.37	9.12	0.87	0.08	0.06
575	1.78	3.16	5.50	10.47	0.86	0.07	0.02
600	1.62	2.95	5.25	9.77	0.84	0.06	0.01
625	1.41	2.82	5.50	11.48	0.80	0.04	0.01
650	1.29	2.69	5.37	12.02	0.75	0.03	0.00
675	1.17	2.57	5.50	12.59	0.67	0.03	0.00
700	1.07	2.45	5.50	13.49	0.58	0.02	0.00
725	0.98	2.29	5.25	13.49	0.48	0.01	0.00
750	0.91	2.24	5.25	14.13	0.39	0.01	0.00

Table 2. Photometric accuracy (σ_m , in magnitudes) per star mapper observation (8+8 slits), and the accuracy of colour determination (σ_{B-V}) per pair of star mapper observations (16 slits at S20 + 16 slits at bialkali).

B	"dark sky" ($B_{sky} = 22.5$)			"bright sky" ($B_{sky} = 20.0$)		
	σ_m (S20)	σ_m (bi)	σ_{B-V}	σ_m (S20)	σ_m (bi)	σ_{B-V}
8	0.03	0.03	0.15	0.05	0.06	0.28
9	0.06	0.06	0.30	0.13	0.14	0.68
10	0.14	0.12	0.66	0.32	0.34	1.67
11	0.34	0.29	1.60	0.80	0.84	4.14

Sky brightness:			$B_{\text{sky}} = 22.5$			$B_{\text{sky}} = 20.0$			$B_{\text{sky}} = 17.5$		
Slit configuration:			A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
S20 sensitivity type	m.e. along y 9	B = 8	.017	.03818	.017	.026	.05326	.028	.068	.13007	.075
		9	.033	.06734	.034	.060	.1206	.065	.17	.3317	.19
		10	.069	.1407	.072	.14	.2814	.16	.42	.8241	.47
		11	.16	.3215	.17	.35	.6834	.39	1.1	2.070	1.2
	m.e. along z 9	B = 8	.041	.036	.042	.058	.053	.061	.14	.13	.16
		9	.076	.067	.077	.13	.12	.14	.35	.33	.39
		10	.15	.14	.16	.30	.28	.33	.87	.82	.96
		11	.34	.31	.36	.73	.68	.80	2.2	2.0	2.4
Bialkali photocathode	m.e. along y 9	B = 8	.016	.03517	.017	.026	.05316	.028	.069	.13065	.077
		9	.030	.06231	.031	.059	.1206	.064	.17	.3317	.19
		10	.058	.1206	.062	.14	.2714	.16	.43	.8341	.48
		11	.13	.2513	.14	.35	.6734	.38	1.1	2.110	1.1
	m.e. along z 9	B = 8	.039	.035	.039	.056	.053	.059	.14	.13	.15
		9	.067	.062	.069	.12	.12	.13	.34	.33	.38
		10	.13	.12	.13	.28	.27	.31	.85	.83	.94
		11	.26	.25	.28	.69	.67	.76	2.1	2.1	2.4

Table 3. Star mapper accuracy (σ_{η} and σ_{ξ} , in arcsec) versus stellar magnitude (Ξ) for a variety of conditions:

- sky brightness $B_{\text{sky}} = 22.5 \text{ mag/arcsec}^2$ ("dark sky"), and 10 x, 100 x
- slit configuration A, B, or C (Fig. 6);
- S20 or bialkali type sensitivity curve.

Fixed parameters: star colour $B-V = 0.6$, sampling rate = 600 Hz.